

Three-dimensional kinematics of competitive and recreational recumbent handcyclists at different sport specific exercise intensities

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Abstract The current knowledge on recumbent handbike configuration and handcycling technique is limited. Thus, the purpose of this study was to evaluate and compare the upper limb kinematics and handbike configurations of recreational (REC) and competitive (COMP) recumbent handcyclists, during sport specific intensities. A secondary objective was to identify characteristics of configuration and technique that were associated with successful performance. Thirteen handcyclists were divided into two discrete groupings based on peak power output; COMP (n=7; 5 H3 and 2 H4 classes; PO_{peak}: 247±20W) and REC (n=6; 4 H3 and 2 H4 classes; PO_{peak}: 198±21 W). Participants performed two five-minute bouts, at moderate (50% PO_{peak}) and vigorous intensity (70% PO_{peak}), and a 20s sprint whilst three-dimensional kinematic data (thorax, scapula, shoulder, elbow and wrist) were collected using a VICON system. Data were normalised to cycle length and statistical parametric mapping was used to compare the kinematics of COMP and REC. Handbike configurations were determined from additional markers on the handbike. COMP flexed their thorax (~5°, P<0.05), extended their shoulder (~10°, P<0.01) and anteriorly tilted their scapular (~15°, P<0.05) more than REC. Differences in scapular motion occurred only at the moderate intensity while differences in shoulder extension and thorax flexion occurred both at moderate and vigorous intensities. No differences were observed during sprinting. No significant differences in handbike configuration were identified. This study is the first to compare the upper limb kinematics of COMP and REC at sport-specific intensities. COMP employed significantly different propulsion strategies at moderate to vigorous intensities. Since no differences in handbike configuration were identified, these kinematic differences could be due to technical training adaptations potentially optimising muscle recruitment or force generation of the arm.

Keywords Recumbent Handcycling, Upper Limb Kinematics, Statistical Parametric Mapping, Disability & Sports Ergonomics

Introduction

Handcycling has increased in popularity at both a recreational and sporting level. Handcycling is an endurance sport, where athletes compete in time trial and road race disciplines. Athletes are classified into one of five categories (H1-H5) according to the nature of their impairment, with H1 being most impaired. Athletes in classes H1-H4 use arm-powered recumbent handbikes.

While the physiological performance determinants of handcycling have been investigated extensively, very little is known about recumbent handcycling biomechanics or handbike configuration. This is critical for the development of the sport, from both a performance and injury perspective. Thus, the current study compared 3D upper limb kinematics and handbike configurations of recumbent handcyclists, differing in performance level, under realistic sports conditions.

Methods

Participants

Thirteen male recumbent handcyclists participated in the study. Participants were divided into two significantly ($P < 0.005$) different groups, recreational and competitive handcyclists, based on their peak aerobic power output (PO_{peak}) that was achieved during a maximal incremental exercise test. This resulted in seven competitive handcyclists (Classification: 5 H3 and 2 H4; PO_{peak}: 247 ± 20 W) who had competed at a national level or higher and six recreational handcyclists (Classification: 4 H3 and 2 H4; PO_{peak}: 198 ± 21 W).

Experimental Protocol

Participants attended the laboratory for two exercise bouts over the course of one day. All exercise bouts were completed at a self-selected cadence and in the participants' recumbent handbikes, which were attached to an ergometer (Cyclus 2, Richter, Germany). Firstly, the participants completed a maximal exercise test to determine their PO_{peak}. After 2 hours of recovery, participants completed two 5-minute exercise bouts, in a randomised order, at a power output equivalent to training (50% PO_{peak}) and competition intensity (70% PO_{peak}) with 5 minutes' rest between trials. Following a further 20 minutes rest, the participants completed a 20-second sprint, from a rolling start, using a resistance equivalent to 5% of their body weight.

Kinematics

A Vicon motion capture system was used to capture upper limb kinematics (thorax, scapula, upper arm, forearm, hand) at training, competition and sprint intensity. Kinematics were analysed over ten complete consecutive cycles. A cycle was defined as one rotation of the crank, starting with the cranks in a vertical position pointing up. Upper limb kinematics were normalised to cycle duration (0% cranks in a vertical position pointing up) and then averaged across the ten cycles. Additional markers were used to measure the participants' anthropometry (arm-length and shoulder width), handbike configuration (crank position, crank width and crank length) and their position on the handbike (shoulder position and eye-line height).

Statistics

One-dimensional statistical parametric mapping (SPM) was used to compare the right arm upper limb kinematics of competitive and recreational handcyclists. An SPM two-tailed independent t-test was used to compare upper limb kinematics at training, competition and sprint intensities allowing the whole kinematic trajectory to be considered (Pataky et al., 2013).

Results

Competitive handcyclists flexed their thorax ($\sim 5^\circ$, $P < 0.05$), extended their shoulder ($\sim 10^\circ$, $P < 0.01$) and posteriorly tilted their scapular ($\sim 15^\circ$, $P < 0.05$) more than recreational handcyclists (Figure 1). These significant differences occurred between 40-75% of the cycle. Differences in scapular motion occurred only at race intensity, while differences in shoulder extension and thorax flexion occurred both at training and race intensity. No differences in kinematics were found when sprinting due to an increase in standard deviation (SD), particularly in the recreational handcyclists. No significant differences in handbike configuration were identified.

Figure 1. Comparison of the thorax and shoulder kinematics (mean kinematic trajectory \pm SD cloud) between competitive (red) and recreational handcyclists (blue) at training, competition and sprint intensities. Shaded regions identify significant differences between groups. P values are provided for each supra-threshold cluster.

Conclusion

This study provided the first comprehensive assessment of recumbent handcycling technique in a sport-specific context. Competitive handcyclists were observed to employ a different propulsion strategy than recreational handcyclists at training and race intensities but not during sprinting. Competitive handcyclists extended their shoulders, flexed their thorax and posteriorly tilted their scapula to a greater extent than recreational handcyclists, during the pull phase of the cycle (25%–75% of the cycle). These technical differences potentially facilitate force generation during the pull phase, contributing to the increased power output of the competitive handcyclists. Since no differences in handbike configuration were identified, these kinematic differences could be due to the differences in skill level between competitive and recreational handcyclists.

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References

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